

Research Article

Investigation of the effects of 8-week environmental control training applied to football players aged 13-16 on football techniques and skills and athletic performance

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Abstract

The study included 30 volunteers aged 13-16, 15 in the experimental group and 15 in the control group, who were trained at Niğde Football Club and the Youth and Sports Directorate. The population of the study consisted of football players aged 13-16. The Mor-Christian General Football Ability Test was used to determine the technical skills of the players, while the Smart Speed Lite photocell was used to determine agility and speed, and the Smart Speed Lite photocell-connected vertical jump mat was used to determine vertical jump performance. SPSS 26 software was used for data analysis, with paired T-tests for within-group comparisons and independent T-tests for between-group comparisons. While there was no significant improvement in football technical skills and athletic performance parameters in the control group's within-group comparison, significant improvements were observed in the experimental group's within-group comparison. In conclusion, the study found that environmental control training had a positive effect on the football technical skills and athletic performance of the players. The reason for this development is that environmental awareness training enables the player to perceive environmental information more quickly, make more accurate decisions, and apply their technical skills at the right time. Therefore, it can be said that there are positive developments in both football technical skills and athletic performance.

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Introduction

Football is a dynamic sport characterized by rapid decision-making, high levels of attention, and continuously changing environmental conditions. In this context, players' environmental awareness and environmental scanning abilities have become crucial determinants of performance. Football is a complex team sport in which physical, technical, tactical, and cognitive components interact within high-tempo and constantly evolving environmental conditions. To perform successfully on the field, players must not only possess technical control of the ball but also be capable of perceiving and rapidly adapting to dynamic changes in their surroundings. Consequently, environmental information gathering (environmental scanning), commonly referred to as environmental scanning behavior or scanning, has become an indispensable component of modern football and serves as a precursor to effective decision-making (Williams et al., 1999; Roca et al., 2013).

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Environmental scanning refers to players' ability to gather information from their surroundings through head and eye movements before receiving the ball, enabling them to develop situational awareness by identifying the positions of teammates and opponents, available space, and directions of pressure (Jordet, 2005). Through this visual search behavior, players mentally process information necessary for planning subsequent actions and making more accurate decisions. Particularly for attacking players, the ability to process such information before receiving possession directly influences game quality and team coordination when making passing, shooting, or dribbling decisions (McGuckian et al., 2018). Environmental scanning is not merely a characteristic unique to elite-level players; rather, it is a cognitive skill that can be systematically trained and developed from an early age (Broadbent et al., 2015).

Previous research has demonstrated that elite players perform more frequent scans before receiving possession and achieve higher passing accuracy compared to less skilled players (Jordet, 2005; Vaeyens et al., 2007). However, scanning behavior may vary according to age, playing experience, and positional role, highlighting the importance of individualized training programs. In an era where technology and science are deeply integrated into everyday life, football has inevitably evolved alongside technological and scientific advancements. With the rapid development of virtual reality (VR) technologies in recent years, new training models and performance-enhancement approaches have emerged within football.

The application of virtual reality technology in competitive sports has created significant opportunities for athlete development and performance analysis. Both national and international research institutions have increasingly focused on performance enhancement and monitoring across various sports disciplines. The widespread adoption of such systems has greatly facilitated athlete education, development, and the achievement of performance objectives expected by coaches and stakeholders. Training within simulated environments, independent of constraints related to time, space, or real-world conditions, can serve numerous purposes in elite sport, including athlete preparation, acquisition of new technical skills, and the practice of specific techniques (Burdea and Coiffet, 2003).

Numerous technical and cognitive parameters contribute to football performance, including positioning, body orientation, environmental scanning, decision-making, identifying passing angles, passing accuracy, and ball control. The importance of these parameters stems from the fast-paced nature of football, where actions must be executed rapidly and players are required to respond effectively to constantly changing game situations. Traditional training methods are often insufficient in replicating the cognitive demands and complexity of situations that developing football players may encounter during competition. Consequently, virtual reality has emerged as a promising tool capable of addressing these limitations. By creating engaging, collaborative, and customizable virtual environments, VR-based interventions provide a safe and structured setting for practicing complex game strategies and decision-making processes (Richlan et al., 2023).

Aim of Study

Despite growing interest in VR applications in sport, randomized controlled studies investigating the combined effects of VR-based training on environmental scanning performance in football players remain limited. Therefore, the present study aimed to evaluate the effects of a VR-based training program that integrates cognitive exercises with football-specific technical tasks on environmental scanning behavior in football players. It was hypothesized that football players receiving the VR-based training intervention would demonstrate significantly greater improvements in environmental scanning performance compared with players who received only traditional training.

Method

Research Design

An experimental research design with a non-equivalent control group was employed in this study (Karasar, 2022). A total of 30 voluntary football players aged between 13 and 16 years participated in the study, including 15 players in the experimental group and 15 players in the control group. The participants were recruited from Niğde Football Club and athletes training under the Provincial Directorate of Youth and Sports, constituting the study sample. The target population of the study consisted of football players aged 13–16 years. While the control group continued their regular

football training programs, the experimental group participated in environmental scanning training sessions (See Appendix 1) three times per week for a period of eight weeks in addition to their routine training.

Data Collection Tools

Mor-Christian General Soccer Ability Test

The Mor-Christian Soccer Ability Test was used to assess the technical skills of the football players. This test evaluates passing, dribbling, and shooting abilities in soccer (Strand and Wilson, 1993).

Dribbling Test

For the dribbling test, twelve cones (45 cm in height) were positioned in a circular formation with 4.5 m intervals within an 18 m diameter testing area. A 1 m starting line was marked outside the circle and perpendicular to it. Upon the command “start,” the player began the test with a stationary ball placed on the starting line. The participant dribbled the ball as quickly as possible around the cones and completed the test upon returning to the starting line. The test was performed in both clockwise and counterclockwise directions. The fastest completion time, recorded in seconds, was included in the analysis (Strand and Wilson, 1993).

Passing Test

A goal measuring 91 cm in width and 45 cm in height was constructed using two cones placed 91 cm apart. A 1.20 m rope was positioned behind the goal line to define a successful pass. Two cones were placed 13.5 m from the goal line at a 45-degree angle, while a third cone was positioned 13.5 m directly in front of the goal line at a 90-degree angle. Passing attempts were performed from each of the three cone positions, with four passes from each location, resulting in a total of 12 passes. Players were allowed to use either foot. One point was awarded for each successful pass. Balls striking the goal cones were also counted as successful. The final passing score was calculated as the sum of successful passes out of the 12 attempts (Strand and Wilson, 1993).

Shooting Test

For the shooting test, four circular targets with a diameter of 1.21 m were positioned inside the goal as described by Strand and Wilson (1993). A shooting line was marked 14.5 m from the goal and parallel to the goal line. Players performed shots from behind the shooting line using stationary balls and were allowed to use either foot. Each of the four target circles was aimed at four times, resulting in a total of 16 shooting attempts.

A score of 10 points was awarded when the ball entered the designated target, whereas 4 points were awarded if the ball entered an incorrect target. For example, a shot directed at the upper-right target received 10 points if successful; however, if it entered a lower target, 4 points were awarded. Only balls that entered the target directly through the air were considered successful. Balls that rolled or bounced into the target were recorded as unsuccessful. The final shooting score was calculated as the sum of the scores obtained from all 16 attempts (Strand and Wilson, 1993).

Agility Test

Agility performance was assessed using the Smart Speed Lite electronic timing gate system (Fusion Sport, Australia). After preparing the test course, photocell timing gates capable of measuring with an accuracy of 0.01 seconds were positioned at the start and finish lines. Agility times were recorded in seconds. The test was performed twice, and participants were given a 10-minute recovery period between trials (Yılmaz and Şengür, 2021; Young, 2002).

Sprint Test

Thirty-meter sprint performance was measured using the Smart Speed Lite electronic timing gate system (Fusion Sport, Australia). The test was performed twice, and the results were recorded in meters per second (m/s). Participants were provided with a 5-minute rest interval between trials (Sevim, 2010; Stølen et al., 2005).

Vertical Jump Test

Vertical jump performance was assessed using the Smart Speed Lite Smart Jump system (Fusion Sport, Australia). Jump height was measured and recorded in centimeters (cm). The test was repeated twice, with a 2-minute recovery period provided between attempts (Petrakis et al., 2019).

Data Analysis

Statistical analyses were conducted using SPSS version 26. The normality of the data distribution was evaluated using the Shapiro–Wilk test, and the data were found to be normally distributed. Paired Samples t-tests were used for within-group comparisons, while Independent Samples t-tests were employed for between-group comparisons. The level of statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Findings

Table 1. Comparison of shooting parameters within the group

Variable	Group	Measurement	N	\bar{X}	Ss	t	p
Shooting (score)	Experiment	Pre-Test	15	43,20	12,95	-14,146	0,001
		Post-Test	15	50,40	13,35		
	Control	Pre-Test	15	48,9	9,70	-,745	0,469
		Post-Test	15	49,46	9,98		

$p < 0.05$.

Table 1 shows that while there was no significant difference in the shooting parameter in the control group, there was a significant difference in the experimental group, with the difference favoring the post-test.

Table 2. Comparison of intra-group passing parameters

Variable	Group	Measurement	N	\bar{X}	Ss	t	p
Passing (piece)	Experiment	Pre-Test	15	7,93	1,16	-9,727	0,001
		Post-Test	15	9,80	0,86		
	Control	Pre-Test	15	8,40	1,24	-,807	0,433
		Post-Test	15	8,53	1,30		

$p < 0.05$.

Table 2 shows that while there was no significant difference in the passing parameter in the control group, there was a significant difference in the experimental group, with the difference favoring the final test.

Table 3. Comparison of intragroup dribbling parameters

Variable	Group	Measurement	N	\bar{X}	Ss	t	p
Dribbling (seconds)	Experiment	Pre-Test	15	19,88	2,33	12,320	0,001
		Post-Test	15	19,70	2,29		
	Control	Pre-Test	15	19,96	1,65	1,380	0,189
		Post-Test	15	19,88	1,55		

Table 3 shows that while there was no significant difference in the ball-handling parameter in the control group, there was a significant difference in the experimental group, with the difference favoring the final test.

Table 4. Comparison of within-group speed parameters

Variable	Group	Measurement	N	\bar{X}	Ss	t	p
Speed (seconds)	Experiment	Pre-Test	15	4,85	0,28	5,954	0,001
		Post-Test	15	4,77	0,25		
	Control	Pre-Test	15	4,91	0,36	1,641	0,123
		Post-Test	15	4,85	0,35		

$p < 0.05$

Table 4 shows that while there was no significant difference in the speed parameter in the control group, there was a significant difference in the experimental group, with the difference favoring the post-test.

Table 5. Comparison of intra-group agility parameters

Variable	Group	Measurement	N	\bar{X}	Ss	t	p
Agility (seconds)	Experiment	Pre-Test	15	16,43	0,50	3,083	0,008
		Post-Test	15	16,29	0,55		
	Control	Pre-Test	15	16,64	0,63	,448	0,661
		Post-Test	15	16,61	0,68		

$p < 0.05$

Table 5 shows that while there was no significant difference in the agility parameter in the control group, there was a significant difference in the experimental group, with the difference favoring the post-test.

Table 6. Comparison of within-group vertical jump parameters

Variable	Group	Measurement	N	\bar{X}	Ss	t	p
Vertical Jump (cm)	Experiment	Pre-Test	15	37,81	3,65	-4,036	0,001
		Post-Test	15	38,03	3,67		
	Control	Pre-Test	15	39,74	4,40	-,907	,380
		Post-Test	15	40,11	4,34		

p < 0.05

Table 6 shows that while there was no significant difference in the vertical jump parameter in the control group, there was a significant difference in the experimental group, with the difference favoring the post-test.

Table 7. Comparison of pre-test parameters between groups

Variables	Group	N	\bar{X}	Ss	t	p
Shooting Pre-Test (Score)	Experiment	15	43,20	12,96	-1,37	,181
	Control	15	48,93	9,71		
Pass Pre-Test (Piece)	Experiment	15	7,93	1,16	-1,06	,297
	Control	15	8,40	1,24		
Dribbling Pre-Test (Seconds)	Experiment	15	19,88	2,33	-0,107	,915
	Control	15	19,96	1,66		
Speed Pre-Test (Seconds)	Experiment	15	4,86	0,29	-0,44	,661
	Control	15	4,91	0,37		
Agility Pre-Test (Seconds)	Experiment	15	16,44	0,51	-0,97	,343
	Control	15	16,64	0,64		
vertical jump pre-test (cm)	Experiment	15	37,81	3,65	-1,31	,201
	Control	15	39,75	4,41		

p < 0.05

Table 7 shows that no significant difference was found when comparing the pre-test results for football technical skills and athletic performance.

Table 8. Comparison of final test parameters between groups

Variables	Grup	N	\bar{X}	Ss	t	p
Shooting Post-Test (Score)	Experiment	15	50,40	13,36	,217	,830
	Control	15	49,47	9,98		
Pass Post-Test (Piece)	Experiment	15	9,80	0,86	3,142	,004
	Control	15	8,53	1,30		
Dribbling Post-Test (Seconds)	Experiment	15	19,70	2,30	-0,252	,803
	Control	15	19,88	1,55		
Speed Post-Test (Seconds)	Experiment	15	4,78	0,25	-0,68	,500
	Control	15	4,85	0,36		
Agility Post-Test (Seconds)	Experiment	15	16,30	0,55	-1,41	,171
	Control	15	16,62	0,68		
Vertical Jump Post-Test (Cm)	Experiment	15	38,03	3,68	-1,42	,168
	Control	15	40,11	4,34		

p < 0.05

Table 8 shows that no significant difference was found in the comparison of shooting and dribbling, and athletic performance post-test results. A difference was found in the passing parameter in the post-test comparison, and this difference was in favor of the experimental group.

Discussion

The positive effects of environmental scanning training on football players' technical skills and athletic performance are primarily attributed to players' ability to perceive and process environmental information more rapidly, thereby enabling more effective decision-making. Players who regularly scan their surroundings before receiving the ball acquire advance information regarding the positions of teammates, opponents, and available space. As a result, they are able to make quicker and more accurate decisions when in possession of the ball, contributing to the development of technical skills such as passing quality, first touch, and dribbling performance. Furthermore, environmental scanning enhances players' game awareness and spatial perception, improving tactical performance by reducing unnecessary movements and enabling the selection of more efficient running paths. Consequently, energy expenditure is optimized, leading to positive effects on athletic performance. Previous research has demonstrated that elite football players perform environmental scanning more frequently and effectively than their less-skilled counterparts, and that this behavior is associated with superior technical execution and overall game performance (Jordet, Bloomfield, and Heijmerikx, 2013; McGuckian et al., 2018).

Accordingly, the aim of the present study was to investigate the effects of an eight-week environmental scanning training program on football-specific technical skills and athletic performance. The comparison of pre-test results revealed no significant differences between the experimental and control groups in terms of football technical skills and athletic performance variables. Similarly, no significant differences were observed between the groups in the post-test comparisons of shooting, dribbling, and athletic performance parameters. However, a significant difference was identified in the post-test comparison of passing performance, favoring the experimental group. Although no statistically significant improvements were observed in the within-group comparison of the control group, positive trends were evident across football technical skill and athletic performance parameters. In contrast, the experimental group demonstrated significant improvements in football technical skills and athletic performance variables in the within-group analyses.

A review of the literature indicates that only a limited number of studies have examined topics directly related to the present research. The improvements in technical skills observed in our study are consistent with the findings of Hunter, Smith, Santiago, and Wilson (2025), who reported a direct relationship between visual scanning behavior and passing performance. These researchers emphasized that effective environmental scanning enhances the quality of technical execution during play. Likewise, the positive effects of the eight-week environmental scanning training program observed by Rudolph et al. (2026) are consistent with recent studies demonstrating the influence of football-specific cognitive-motor training on perceptual and performance outcomes. In particular, cognitive stimuli delivered within the actual playing environment have been shown to transfer more effectively to game performance.

Similarly, Erişik, Cerrah, and Çınarlı (2025) reported that a seven-week cognitive-technical environmental scanning training program significantly improved players' scanning behaviors and passing performance. These findings suggest that environmental scanning skills play a critical role in decision-making and the quality of technical execution during match play. Furthermore, the present results support the findings of Scharfen and Memmert (2021), who identified a positive relationship between perceptual-cognitive performance and football-specific performance. These authors reported that players with superior capacities for processing environmental information demonstrated higher passing accuracy and overall game performance.

Limitations of Study

The study included male soccer players aged 13-16. The experimental group received only environmental awareness training in addition to their routine soccer training.

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Appendix 1. Environmental Control Training Protocol

Environmental Control Training Protocol			
Week	Monday	Wednesday	Friday
1 st Week	<p>Warm-Up (20 min.) Ball warm-up activities</p> <p>Technical Ball mastery and ball familiarity exercises Inside-foot passing drills Set-piece practice Short-distance ground passes (towards a large target) Dribbling using all surfaces of both feet in a balanced and symmetrical manner</p> <p>Skill Development Equal use of both feet Light running with the ball while maintaining close control</p> <p>Game: 3 vs. 3 small-sided games 5 vs. 5 small-sided games</p> <p>Cool-Down (5 min.) Stretching exercises</p> <p>Key Coaching Points Scanning (environmental awareness) Communication First touch quality Knowing where and how to dribble Using both short and long touches while dribbling Finishing the action with a pass, shot, or cross after dribbling</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Ball Warm-Up</p> <p>Technical: Ball Familiarization, Dribbling and Ball Control</p> <p>Skill Development: Equal use of both feet. Light running with the ball while maintaining control.</p> <p>Game: 3v3, 5v5</p> <p>Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching</p> <p>Key Coaching Points: Scanning (environmental awareness), communication, first touch, where and how to dribble (using short and long touches), finishing the action with a pass, shot, or cross after dribbling, and providing support to teammates.</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Ball Warm-Up</p> <p>Technical: Ball Familiarization, Dribbling, and Ball Control</p> <p>Skill Development: Equal use of both feet. Light running with the ball while maintaining close control.</p> <p>Game: 3v3, 5v5</p> <p>Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching</p> <p>Key Coaching Points: Scanning (environmental awareness) Communication First touch Knowing where and how to dribble (using short and long touches) After dribbling, finish the action with a pass, shot, or cross Provide support to teammates and create passing options.</p>
2 nd Week	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball.</p> <p>Technique: Ball handling, turns with the ball.</p> <p>Skill: Equal use of both feet.</p> <p>Game: 5x5 game with right and left turns.</p> <p>Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching.</p> <p>Key Factors: Situational awareness, Communication, Decision moment (full turn, half turn), First touch, Finishing.</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball.</p> <p>Technique: Ball handling, dribbling, and spatial awareness.</p> <p>Skill: Both feet working equally.</p> <p>Game: Dribbling and passing in a 7x7 game.</p> <p>Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching.</p> <p>Key Factors: First touch, Look at the ball when touching it, Look ahead while running, Cover the distance as quickly as possible, Take a short step for the moment of decision, Execute your decision (pass, shoot, cross).</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball.</p> <p>Technique: Ball handling, dribbling and spatial awareness.</p> <p>Skill: Equal work of both feet.</p> <p>Game: In a 40x30 m area, players try to carry the ball (dribbling) and reach the 2 m area at the end of the field by controlling the pass within 2 m.</p> <p>Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching. KEY Factors: Spatial awareness, Communication, First touch, Where - how to dribble (with short and long passes), Finishing</p>
3 rd Week	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball.</p> <p>Technique: Ball control, dribbling, ball handling.</p> <p>Skill: Equal use of both feet.</p> <p>Game: In a 60m x 15m area, using dribbling, ball handling, and vertical passes to advance and finish attacks.</p> <p>Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching.</p> <p>Key Factors: Leave the player with the ball in a 1v1 situation. Dribble the ball quickly towards the opponent. Be aggressive and positive. Decision moment. Execute your decision. Pass the ball. Support and finish.</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball.</p> <p>Technique: Ball Aptitude, Ball Control.</p> <p>Skill: Both feet work equally.</p> <p>Game: Played 7:7, 8:8. Work is done conditionally. (2 touches, 3 touches, etc.)</p> <p>Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching. KEY Factors: Awareness of the surroundings, movement towards the ball, first touch (body shape), flexibility and softness with the ball, finishing.</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball.</p> <p>Technique: Ball handling, passing and control drills.</p> <p>Skill: Equal work with both feet.</p> <p>Game: Can be played in a designated area with 5:5, 6:6, or 7:7 formations. During free play, focus is placed on players' passing and ball control.</p> <p>Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching. KEY Factors: Situational awareness, Communication, Creating space, Passing quality, First touch</p>
4 th Week	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball.</p> <p>Technique: Ball Aptitude, Ball Control.</p> <p>Skill: Both feet work equally.</p> <p>Game: Ball control is emphasized during free play in the training.</p> <p>Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching.</p> <p>Key Factors: Situational awareness, Communication, Mobility First touch, Passing, shooting, dribbling</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball.</p> <p>Technique: Ball control, passing.</p> <p>Skill: Equal use of both feet.</p> <p>Game: Played 5:5 in 3 teams. One team is outside the area. Whichever team has the ball inside the 5:5 team can pass to the players outside the area. The teams inside and outside take turns.</p> <p>Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching.</p> <p>Key Factors: Situational control Creating space Communication First touch Passing quality Stay calm under pressure Protect the ball Finishing Turning top</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball.</p> <p>Technique: Ball handling, passing and control drills.</p> <p>Skill: Equal work with both feet.</p> <p>Game: Normal game is played. A goal scored counts as 1 goal. An extra 7 passes count as 1 goal.</p> <p>Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching. KEY Factors: Situational awareness, Communication, Creating space, Passing quality, First touch, Finishing</p>

<p>5th Week</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball. Technique: Ball handling, turning and passing drills. Skill: Equal work with both feet. Game: Played in 5:5, 6:6, 7:7 formations. The use of all turns is encouraged during the game. Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching. Key Factors: Perimeter control, Creating space, Deceptive runs, Decision moment (turning styles), Finishing.</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball. Technique: Ball handling, shots, stopping, volleys Skill: Equal use of both feet. Game: A game is played. To score a goal, stopping, volleys, and half-volleys must be used. 2 points are awarded for goals scored with stopping and volleys. Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching. Key Factors: Eye on the ball, speed of approach to the ball, body angle, first touch (inside, outside, top of the foot)</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball. Technique: Ball handling, one-two passes. Skill: Equal work with both feet. Game: Played in 3 teams. If 2 teams play inside the court and make a wall pass with the players outside, they score 1 point. Similarly, if the other team inside wins the ball, they try to score a point with a wall pass. The exercise ends within the time determined by the coach, and the teams outside and inside switch places. Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching. Key Factors: Situational awareness, Communication, Body angle, First touch, Striking techniques, Pass quality, Support</p>
<p>6th Week</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball. Technique: Ball control, one-two passes. SKILL: Equal use of both feet. Game: Played in a 50x40m area with a 7:7 or 8:8 formation. 2 points are awarded for a goal scored after a one-two pass. Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching. Key Factors: Situational awareness, Communication, Pass quality, First touch, Timing, Finishing</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball. Technique: Ball control, one-two passes. Skill: Equal use of both feet. Game: 1 goalkeeper, 6 players, 2 teams on a 40x50m area. 3rd team waits outside. Teams are switched according to time. The aim is to develop one-two passes. The field is divided into 3 sections with lines. Entering each section with a one-two pass earns 1 point for the teams. Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching. Key Factors: Situational awareness, Communication, Body angle, First touch, Striking techniques, Quality of pass, Support</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball. Technique: Ball handling, developing the weaker foot. Skill: Both feet work equally. Game: All variations are allowed in the game. However, no player can touch the ball with their stronger foot. That is, every player must use their weaker foot. The aim is to develop the weaker foot, position yourself according to your weaker foot, and use your body. Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching. Key Factors: Body angle, frequent contact with the ball. Ball control quality, passing quality.</p>
<p>7th Week</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball. Technique: Ball control, dribbling, shooting Skill: Equal work with both feet. Game: Shooting practice with 3 goals each, played 5:5, 6:6. Teams protect 3 goals while trying to score in the other 3. Goals scored after dribbling count as 2. Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching. Key Factors: Situational awareness, Creating space, Mobility, First touch (long - short, what for?), Decision (long step - short step), Finishing Spinning ball</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball. Technique: Ball handling, shooting Skill: Equal use of both feet. Game: Played 6:6, 7:7 in a designated area. The aim is accuracy in shooting. The goal is to shoot without entering the designated area; this counts as 2. Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching. Key Factors: Situational awareness, Decision, Shot quality (where, how), Finishing, Rebounding ball</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball. Technique: Ball control, dribbling, and shooting. Skill: Equal use of both feet. Game: Played 8:8 in a designated area. Goals scored with a shot after dribbling or from a distance count as 2 points. Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching. KEY Factors: Awareness of the situation; Dribbling the ball forward with determination and speed; Be positive and aggressive; Implement your decisions (dribbling skills); Finishing; Rebounding ball.</p>
<p>8th Week</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball. Technique: Ball control, shooting Skill: Equal use of both feet. Game: The training area can be oval or rectangular. The aim is to shoot while each player stays in their own area. Blue players try to shoot after making at least 3 passes in their own area. The two red players in the opponent's area try to press. The two blue players in the opponent's area can score by following up the shot or winning the ball from the opponent. Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching. Key Factors: Situational awareness, Decision moment, Shot quality, Rebounding ball</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball. Technique: Ball control, shooting Skill: Equal work with both feet. Game: Blue and red teams play inside, while yellow players take their positions near the goal. If a goal is scored after a pass from a yellow player, 2 points are awarded. Then the yellow players and the inside teams switch places and the game continues. Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching. Key Factors: First touch. Decide. (what kind of shot) Look at the target first, then look at the ball while shooting. Aim at the target first. Then the power of the ball. Finishing/Rebounding ball</p>	<p>Warm-Up: 20 min. Warm-up with the ball. Technique: Ball handling, throw-in. Skill: Equal work of both feet. Game: Free play is played during the training, with an emphasis on ball control. Cool-Down: 5 min. Stretching. KEY Factors: Body position, Communication, Ball between hands, feet firmly on the ground, ball going over the head, Appropriate throw-in (long, short), Support.</p>